

MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES OF TAMIL NADU HANDLOOM WEAVERS CO-OPERATIVE SOCIETY (CO-OPTEX) FOR INCLUSIVE GROWTH

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1. Introduction

The Tamil Nadu Handloom Weavers Co-operative Society (Co-optex) is the largest Handloom Co-operative Society in India. The multicolored Butterfly logo identifies its quality and fair trade in handlooms sector in India. This has been possible because of its foundation of highly experienced and skilled weavers producing handlooms representing a historic weaving tradition of Tamil Nadu with unmatched aesthetic quality.

Today, Co-optex is a symbol of the Highest tradition of handlooms in India and is providing sustained employment to the weavers of the State with great social cause.

The Co-optex was established in 1935 under the co-operative Society Act, with the main objective of organizing and promoting handloom industry for development of handloom weavers in co-operative sector on a commercial basis.

The Co-optex is continuously striving to accomplish the main objectives of

1. Extending market support to Weavers' Co-operative Societies and popularizing handloom products,
2. Implementing various innovative schemes
3. Creating continuous employment opportunities for handloom weavers.
4. To develop products that combine tradition and fashion to meet the changing demand of customers.

Co-optex was established in 1935 and is able to reach its customers through its 192 Showrooms spread across the country. Co-optex has the distinction of being geographically, the most spread Apex society with outstanding contribution to Handlooms in the country.

Due to its dedicated work force and experience in handling the Government schemes, Co-optex has been appointed as one of the nodal agencies for Cost Free Distribution of Sarees and Dhothies Scheme, Free supply of School Uniform Scheme to school students and exclusively for Old Age Pension Scheme.

Co-optex International is exporting Home textiles products to the countries like Germany, Belgium, Spain, United Kingdom, Italy and France.

2. Objectives of Co optex

The functions are to procure and supply raw materials to the primary weaver's co-operative societies and extend marketing support. It has 413 outlets out of which 250 within the State and 163 outside Tamil Nadu. Co-optex procures the production of the primary co-operative societies. Regarding Janatha Cloth and polyester yarns the entire production of the primary societies is procured by Co-optex.

In tune with the fast changing fashions and consumer-preferences and to meet the growing demand in the internal and international markets for new handloom products, it has been recognized that the handloom industry should also adopt modern techniques of weaving. Any technology appropriate to the handloom industry would involve three distinct objectives viz. reduction of costs, improving quality of the product and reducing fatigue on the part of the weavers. For this purpose the handloom co-operatives in the state are being encouraged to undertake renovations/modernizations of looms or to purchase new modern looms. Retail Sales during 2017-2018 During the year 2017-2018, Co-optex has achieved a sales of Rs.316.15 crore. This sales was a result of many initiatives including continuous procurement throughout the year, modernization of a large number of showrooms to improve the ambience of the showrooms, increased design interventions, introduction of new products, as well as recruitment motivation and training to the new staff. The effective marketing through Social Media Campaigning has improved the customer base and resulted in large number of first time buyers patronising Co-optex products.

Table 1

Table showing the details of Retail Sales during 2015-2016 TO 2017-2018

Sl.No	Duration in Years	Rupees (in Lakhs)
1	2015-2016	313
2	2016-2017	315
3	2017-2018	316

Source : Secondary data (Tamil nadu policy note , Demand Number 17)

Table. 2

Table showing the details of Product wise Sales during 2017-2018

Sl. No	Duration in Years	Rupees (in Lakhs)
1	SAREES	56
2	DHOTIES/LUNGIES	5
3	TOWWELS	5
4	HOME DECCOR	25
5	READY MADES	2
6	OTHERS	7

Source : Secondary data (Tamil nadu policy note , Demand Number 17)

3. Marketing Department

A broad vision of the marketing objectives was prominent by its absence among Primary Weavers' Cooperatives. However, the Cooptex has spelt out the objective of marketing clearly. Neither the Cooptex nor the Primary Weavers' Cooperatives had a separate department for 'marketing'. In the Cooptex, there was a department named 'marketing'. But, it attended primarily to 'selling' rather than marketing. Other functions like product design and development, market research, export etc., were kept out of this department. In Primary Weavers' Cooperatives, a few marketing functions had been allocated to subordinates below the rank of the Manager or Secretary.

3.1. Target Markets.

Weavers' Cooperatives in Tamil Nadu have accepted a multi-segment approaches and identified their target consumers on the basis of level of income, sex and geographical location. They had a better perception of consumer preference of and product features for different segments of the market.

4. Product Strategy Product Mix.

The product Mix of Weavers' Cooperatives in Tamilnadu consisted of more than one product line with large number of items in each line, contributing to the depth of the product line. However, the product line of the silk weaving societies was relatively narrow as compared to the other two categories of societies. Nevertheless, the Cooptex dealt with all items of handloom fabrics that are produced by PUCSs.

4.1. Product Mix-Expansion and Product Mix-Contraction Strategy.

Weavers' Cooperatives in Tarnilnadu adopted both the expansion and contraction strategies. The Government played a catalytic role in this regard.

4.2. Branding Strategy.

Branding was popular at the Cooptex level as well as among silk weaving. societies, while labelling was predominant among other primary societies.

4.3. Product Design and Development.

Product Design and Development as a strategy was adopted by weavers' Cooperatives in Tarnilnadu. Product Development was done by the Cooptex mostly by acquiring new product concepts, and they were transferred to PUCSs for adoption. However, the Cooptex evaluated such new designs with regard to technical feasibility, market acceptability etc. , before cotnmer c ialisation.

4. Pricing Strategy Pricing Method.

Weavers' Cooperatives including the Cooptex followed 'Coat Plus Pricing Method* with 'Differential Mark Lips' to fix 'Base Price' for their products. 27 2 Price-Off Strategy. Weavers' Cooperatives including the

Cooptex allowed various types of Price-off, such as consumer rebate, consumer discount, special discount, VIP's discount, trade discount, trade commission and allowances.

5. Price Discrimination Strategy.

The Cooptex alone adopted price discrimination among the buyers of fabrics on geographical basis. Thus, hand loom weavers' Cooperatives have adopted cost as well as market oriented pricing strategy along with appropriate promotion measures.

6. Marketing Strategies of Co optex

6.1 Co-optex Online Sales

Co-optex has introduced online sales through its own portal to attract more number of customers and tech savvy generation across the country. As the customers support is encouraging, Co-optex has enlarged its products range to include products like Linen Shirts, Kurthis, Organic Sarees, Quilt & Home Furnishing on its Online portal. Co-optex today achieved No.1 in online sales amongst all handloom Apex Societies in India. The online sales is showing an impressive growth since inception.

Table. 3

Table showing the details of online sales

Sl. No	Year	Rupees in Lakh
1	2014-2015	5.14
2	2015-2016	32.96
3	2016-2017	58.52
4	2017-2018	102

International Portal In order to facilitate online purchase and delivery to customers across the globe, Co-optex has established International shipment facility from 31.01.2018 on its online portal. During the year 2017-18, Co-optex has doubled its sale to Rs.1.02 crore through Online Portal as compared to last year.

6.2. Modernisation of Showrooms

Co-optex has modernized the its Showrooms in 1.Deepam, Vellore 2.Tiruvannamalai 3.Tenkasi 4.Muthunagar, Tuticorin 5.Srivilliputhur As a result of the success of the Home Tex at T.Nagar, Chennai in the year 2017-2018, an exclusive showroom for home furnishing, another Home Tex showroom has been opened at Co-optex Marudham Showroom at Coimbatore.

6.3. Design Innovations

Co-optex has introduced new designs to cater to contemporary tastes. the Co-optex Design Studios in Chennai had hired expert designers trained at the National Institute of Designs to focus on the urban clients and customers by attracting them with combinations and patterns involving pastel shades, zero zari silk saris and combining two or more traditional silk weaving centre novelties. The zero zari silk sari with threaded work has become a hit with the upmarket customers and working professionals who prefer elegance with simplicity.

Considering the changing needs and preference of its customers, Co-optex has introduced a large number of new designs through its own Design Studio. In the year 2017-2018, 2000 new designs in various products were introduced. Introduction of New Products Co-optex introduced new products keeping in mind the taste of urban customers in the year 2017-2018.

AHIMSA silk sarees: The silk yarn used for the production of these sarees is spun from silk cocoons without killing the silk worms and hence the name - Ahimsa Silk Sarees. Ahimsa silk sarees are woven by the Handloom Weavers in Kancheepuram and Arani area.

Natural Dyed Cotton Sarees: The cotton yarn used in the Production of these sarees is dyed with Natural colours extracted from flowers, herbs, petals, leaves, seeds etc. These saree are made out of high quality combed cotton yarn and woven by the weavers of Vadambachery in Pollachi, Dindigul and Manamedu area in Tiruchirappalli district.

New Kanchi Cotton Sarees: The specially designed New Kanchi Cotton Sarees incorporating traditional designs in pure thread work has been revived and produced by the skilled weavers of Vadambachery, Dindigul and Paramakudi Weaving Cluster. These meticulously woven sarees using 80s fine quality yarn are

incorporated with traditional motifs in contemporary style. These sarees with rich thread work pallu exhibit grand look of the Kanchee cotton sarees.

Mens' Combo Pack/ Velcro Dhothy: Keeping in mind its male customers Co-optex has introduced Men's Combo Pack, a set consisting of one dhothy and one matching cotton shirting piece for sales across Co-optex showrooms. Co-optex has developed Velcro Dhothy specially for Dhothy lovers and for people not adept in wearing the dhothy. These are provided with Velcro tape and a pocket to keep wallet and mobiles. These Dhothies are available in different sizes.

For the festival season, the organisation has introduced a variety of saris, from silk ikat prints to handwoven and hand block-printed cotton creations. Co-optex has launched handwoven silk and cotton stoles and dupattas, mimicking designs and borders of double jacquard saris. These are made by weavers in Vadambachery, Arupukottai, Vanavasi and Manamedu areas. Silk stoles are made by weavers from the Arni region.

6.4. Exhibition/Trade Shows.

Co-optex has 200 showrooms across the country but its handloom products are in demand in other towns and cities also. It developed an exhibition calendar on the lines of the Central Silk Board and the National Handloom Development Corporation. The Cooptex had organised/ participated in exhibitions during October-December months. The rate of participation in the exhibitions by PUCSs remained high. However, the number of exhibitions participated/organised by the Cooptex had been declining year after year owing to declining consumer response.

6.5. National Handloom Expo-Hand Tex 2017

With an objective to create awareness on the importance of handlooms, the Government of Tamil Nadu decided to celebrate Handloom Day on 7th August. Co-optex, in co-ordination with Department of Handlooms and Textiles, Chennai, conducted, a National Handloom Expo – named "HAND TEX 2017" at Kalaivanar Arangam, Chennai. In all, 44 Stalls were put up by Co-optex and other Handloom organizations from across the country. Co-optex has an exhibition of wedding collection silk sarees at its outlet and also offer discount to customers for purchases during this period.

This event became major driving force to promote the sales of Handloom products and achieved a sale of Rs.1.62 Crore within a span of 7 days.

Table. 4

Table showing the details of sales of Handloom products in HAND TEX 2017

S. No.	Details	Value (Rs. in lakh)
1	Value of Sales by Co-optex	96.13
2	Value of Sales other State apex Societies	65.43
3	Total	161.56

6.6. Fashion Show

To highlight the significance of handloom to younger generation and fashion conscious elite, a fashion show was organized in co-ordination with NIFT Chennai. The Fashion show titled "Symphony of Weaves" had region specific sequences, showing handlooms produced across Tamil Nadu.

Weaver's Identity Card Hand weaving, as a craft is passed on from one generation to another and requires immense patience and skill to master it. Co-optex provides traceability for all its handloom sarees by attaching Weaver Cards. These weaver's Identity Cards provide a connect between the weaver and the customer.

6.7. Sales Promotion Schemes

Buy 2 Get 1 Free: An innovative scheme Buy 2 Get 1 Free scheme was launched in the year 2011-2012. The scheme is continued due to encouraging response. During 2017-2018, Co-optex has achieved a sales of Rs. 35 Crore through this scheme. In an effort to support the weavers of Tamil Nadu and to give them a recognition, an exhibition-cum-sale was inaugurated on Friday at Co-optex, Suryabagh. From silk and cotton sarees to bedsheets, carpets and towels, the scheme 'Buy two, get one free' was launched. Co-optex launched a special sale promotion offer "Aadiyil Athirstam", during the Tamil month of Aadi i.e., from 14.07.2017 to 13.08.2017 to compete with the special discounts offered by private retail stores and achieved a sales of Rs.20.13 crore.

Kanavu Nanavu Thittam: Co-optex offers a popular monthly savings scheme named as "Kanavu Nanavu Thittam". Customer can invest through monthly installments starting from Rs.300/- and multiples of Rs.100/-. Customer pays 9 monthly installments and Co-optex pays the 10th installment. In this scheme, the customer reaps 58% cash benefit on their 9 month savings. 36,000 customers have been enrolled under this scheme. During the year 2017-2018 a sales of Rs.13.62 crore has been achieved under this scheme. A sale of around Rs.24 crore is anticipated during the year 2018-2019.

Thanga Mazhai Thittam: To promote cash sale during festival seasons (15.09.2017 to 31.01.2018) covering Deepavali, Christmas and Pongal, Co-optex introduced "Thanga Mazhai Thittam". Each customer, who buys products for Rs.2000/- and in multiples in cash or by credit / debit card, contest coupons are issued. Under this scheme a total of 1.10 Kg Gold coins were distributed to 220 customers.

7. Promotion Strategy Advertising.

The Co optex being a marketing organisation of PUCSS, used three major advertising media, namely, print, broadcast and other media. Advertisements were made only during festival periods. Among these media, however, broadcast media, particularly television was extensively used. The advertisement programme of primaries was handicapped by limited media choice.

7.1. Sales Promotion.

The Weavers' Cooperatives in Tamilnadu used various sales promotion tools, which include consumer rebate and various forms of discounts. The Cooptex adopted a large number of sales promotional tools besides 'rebate'. 273 Although promotional tools were adopted selectively by PUCSS, the silk weaving societies adopted many promotional tools compared to others. Promotion measures were conspicuous by their absence among the mixed fabrics weaving aoci eties.

7.2. Credit Sale.

The Cooptex adopted credit sale as a sales promotional device in both direct and indirect channels. Further, it assumed significance over the years. In PUCSS credit sale was confined only to the Cooptex. However, the need for credit sale was greater in respect of rnade-ups/carpet and mixed fabrics than in respect of silk.

7.3. Prize Award Scheme for the Best Exporters

With a view to encourage the handloom export and to augment the sale of handloom products in the international market, the Government of Tamil Nadu was implemented the Best Exporters' Award since 1975.

Under this scheme a sum of Rs.1.00 lakh per annum was provided to distribute Trophies and Certificate to the Best Exporters and Primary Weavers' Co-operative Societies.

7.4. Prize Award Scheme for the Best Talented Weavers

To encourage the handloom weavers, the Government implemented Prize Award Scheme every year for the Best Weavers who are involved in developing new designs in cotton and silk varieties. The prize for the best designs is as follows:-

First prize	Rs.5,000/-
Second prize	Rs.3,000/-
Third prize	Rs. 2,000/-

Implementation of this scheme helps to collect marketable varieties with new innovative designs. The expenditure under this scheme was taken from the Research and Development Fund of Tamil Nadu Co-operative Union.

7.5. Personal Selling

Personal selling was a major component in the promotion mix of weavers' Cooperatives in general and the Cooptex in particular. The sales force was provided with pecuniary and non-pecuniary incentives. Yet, effective control measures such as the assignment of responsibilities by sales quotas, their performance appraisal, skill development, sales force size optimization were not introduced in the Cooptex. However, in Primary Weavers' Cooperatives, personal selling was not in vogue.

8. Distribution Strategy

Weavers' Cooperatives in Tamil Nadu have adopted Dual/Multi-channel strategy. Direct channel was the principal channel of the Co-optex and silk weaving societies while indirect channel was prominent in the carpet/made-ups weaving, and mixed fabrics weaving societies.

8.1. Direct Channel.

The Weavers' Cooperatives established exclusive as well as inclusive showrooms as a part of their direct channel. The Co-optex had established its own sales net work by organising exclusive retail showrooms all over the country. Majority of its retail showrooms were located in home state and their number had increased year after year, whereas it was on the decline in other states which speaks about inefficient channel management. Among PUCSs, a significant percentage of the silk weaving and cat-pet/made up a weaving societies had their own retail showrooms which reveal their successful adoption of direct channel. The Co-optex had different type of showrooms to cater to the diverse needs of the different market segments. The silk weaving societies alone had inclusive showrooms as a pooled marketing strategy. The exclusive showroom was not popular among the carpet/made-ups weaving and mixed fabrics weaving societies.

8.2. Indirect Channel.

A variety of indirect channels of distribution were available to handloom cooperatives. In PUCSs, next to the Co-optex, private dealers were the popular channel intermediaries. However, no mixed fabrics weaving societies had exclusive dealer either within or outside Tamilnadu. Cooperatives and government corporations were the only channel intermediaries of the Cooptex. However, sales made to them had recorded a declining trend. Further the consumers' cooperative as a channel was not effectively used.

8.3. Export Trade of the Cooptex.

The weaving societies had the largest share in the total export of the Cooptex and largest share of the export was made to European countries followed by South East Asian countries. The Cooptex had shown good progress in its export trade which indicates the growing market potentials for handloom fabrics in foreign countries.

8.4. Physical Distribution Strategy.

The regional offices of the Cooptex played an important role in the physical distribution functions such as storage and warehousing, inventory control, inventory movement, order processing etc. Inventory stock was maintained in all retail showrooms throughout the year in anticipation of demand. The Cooptex adopted "Dispersed Inventory Location Strategy". The stock held within Tamilnadu was higher than that in outside Tamilnadu. However, the percentage of stock held outside Tamilnadu had increased in recent years. Among PUCSs, no systematic practice was in vogue in respect of physical distribution functions.

9. Conclusion

Co-optex aims to achieve a target sale by developing new designs, introducing new products, further modernization of the showrooms, wide publicity and by canvassing more orders from the Government Departments.

The Co-optex may take the following measures to strengthen their marketing system to achieve a target sale.

1. The Co-optex should adopt the complete accountability of supplying raw materials required by the primaries in adequate quantities and loom spare parts.
2. The expenditure acquired by the weavers for change-over from one design to another and one item to another may be borne by the society, whenever the society gives directions for such change over.
3. The performance may be evaluated in terms of achievements of salesmen, sales quotas and contribution to the achieve organizational goals. To motivate salesmen, salary structure of salesmen may be designed and to provide commission on sales performance.
4. The Co-optex may re-design its existing organizational structure. An integrated marketing department under the leadership of marketing manager, incorporating such functions as product design and development, procurement of fabrics, export trade, advertisement, marketing research and information may be created. This would introduce greater degree of specialisation and lead to more effective planning, implementation and control of marketing functions.

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